

Visigothic script versus Caroline minuscule: the collision of two cultural worlds in twelfth-century Galicia¹

1. Preamble

It was not until the second decade of the twelfth century that Caroline minuscule started to be used in Galicia, in the far north-western corner of the Iberian Peninsula, closing the cycle of more than 400 years of use of Visigothic script as the main graphic system in Iberia. A new period of openness to European cultural currents put then an end to the last vestige of the graphical and liturgical particularism that characterised medieval Iberia, which had begun to fade in the easternmost territories as soon as in the ninth century. The process of change meant a drastic transformation for all literate and illiterate people alike that was not received with equal eagerness in all areas or by all centres. Some ecclesiastical institutions, led by ambitious bishops and abbots, saw an opportunity to grow and present themselves as the new main cultural centres of medieval Iberia, taking away the political and cultural prominence of those that had once been instrumental in the reorganisation of the Christian peninsular realms after the Muslims' arrival. Others seem to have been reluctant to accept a new rite and to adopt a new script, neither of which was a national product. Caroline minuscule had not evolved gradually, like Visigothic script had, from the previous documentary and book hand writing systems used, but was imposed, like the Roman rite, mostly by political interests of kings, ecclesiastical elites, and cultural pressure. Acceptance of change would lead to a cultural unification with centres outside Iberia in which the glorious Visigothic past, the characteristically Iberian Visigothic script, and the Visigothic rite were no more than a memory. In analysing the extant manuscript sources, codices and charters, that speak of this liturgical imposition and graphical acculturation, the present work discusses not only how the process occurred but what it must have meant, politically and culturally speaking, for major cultural northern peninsular institutions both old and new; for those closer to what was the Carolingian Empire and for those geographically distant but very much in the political and ecclesiastical centre of Christian Iberia. After a historical and graphical review of how the process of change developed in Septimania and Catalonia already in the ninth century, and in Aragon, Navarre, and the Leonese-Castilian kingdoms well into the eleventh century, attention will be given to Galicia for its peculiarity. A thorough look at the late-eleventh and mid-twelfth-century extant sources produced in the two main Galician dioceses, Lugo and Santiago de Compostela, and their historical contextualisation, highlights the steps of graphical and cultural change simultaneously providing valuable evidence about how the transition from the

¹ This article is an abridged version of the work with the same title presented by the author as LMS dissertation at the Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies in 2015. The research leading to these results has been supported by grants from the Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies (Andrew W. Mellon Postdoctoral Fellowship) and the Center for Epigraphical and Palaeographical Studies at Ohio State University (Virginia Brown Fellowship in Latin Palaeography). The author wishes to thank all the many people who have contributed to this discussion. Special thanks are due to Prof. Greti Dinkova-Bruun.

old Visigothic script system to the new European Caroline minuscule one must have been experienced by the scribes and copyists who lived it.

2. Context: The introduction of Caroline minuscule and the Roman rite in the Iberian Peninsula

The Synods of Burgos and Leon, in 1080 and 1090 respectively, have been seen as a turning point for the cultural evolution of the Iberian Peninsula, marking a definitive transition from early medieval Christian kingdoms firmly attached to their Visigothic past to kingdoms fully integrated within Europe. In Burgos, the liturgical unification firmly advocated by Pope Gregory VII and aiming to replace the Hispanic rite with the Roman rite, finally took place;² in Leon, the homogenisation of ecclesiastical practice went further, reaching its graphical equivalent with the adoption of Caroline minuscule script for liturgical texts. However, as always happens with political identities that are not isolated from each other, the Frankish cultural influence in the Iberian peninsular territories evident in both councils can be identified long before that moment, as can the resistance to it after 1090. The final change of the liturgy and the substitution of one writing system for another took place through a slow and gradual process, reaching different stages in each of the northern Christian kingdoms as a result of the combination of religious and cultural aspects as well as specific political circumstances.

The Frankish influence was perceived particularly early in Septimania, the Visigothic province in southern France, and the territories that would become the Catalan counties, in the northeast of the Iberian Peninsula. There the Roman rite and Caroline minuscule were adopted first as a consequence of the close geographical and political connections with the Carolingian Empire. After the Muslims brought the Visigothic kingdom to an end and reached the south of what is now France in 719, conquering Narbonne's territories and threatening the Frankish realms, Carolingian rulers became directly involved in trying to stop their advance. After several confrontations, they succeeded, regaining Septimania and forcing the invaders to draw back. In the late eighth century, Charlemagne established the Frankish protectorate known as the Spanish March as a defensive barrier south of the Pyrenees.³ Both Septimania and this newly reorganised territory, divided into counties, were immediately thereafter under Frankish direct political, civil, and ecclesiastical jurisdiction. The reclaimed territories were then ecclesiastically attached to Narbonne's metropolitan see, thus adopting in the early ninth century the Roman liturgy and new monastic and canonical rules in cathedral schools and eventually also in peripheral centres.

The fluid exchange of codices across the Pyrenees through this Carolingian area of the peninsula which had stopped because of previous political instability, increased thereafter as can be glimpsed, for example, in the rich library the monastery of Ripoll already had in the early tenth century

² For the differences between the rites, see R. E. Reynolds, "The Ordination Rite in Medieval Spain: Hispanic, Roman, Hybrid," in *Santiago, Saint-Denis, and Saint Peter: the reception of the Roman liturgy in Leon-Castile in 1080*, ed. B. F. Reilly (New York, 1985), 131-155; Id., "Baptismal rite and paschal vigil in transition in medieval Spain: a new text in Visigothic script," *Mediaeval Studies* 55 (1993): 257-272; Id., "The Visigothic liturgy in the realm of Charlemagne," in *Das Frankfurter Konzil von 794: 4. Kristallisationspunkt karolingischer Kultur*, ed. R. Berndt (Mainz, 1997), 919-945. For a full comparison, see R. Walker, *Views of Transition: Liturgy and Illumination in Medieval Spain* (London-Toronto, 1998), particularly chapter 6.

³ For a summary on the topic, see S. Barton, "Spain in the eleventh century," in *The New Cambridge Medieval History vol. 4: c.1024-c.1198*, ed. D. Luscombe and J. Riley-Smith (Cambridge, 2004), 154-190 (162); R. Collins, *Early Medieval Spain: Unity in Diversity, 400-1000*, 2d ed. (London, 1995).

testifying to the pro-European interests of north-eastern peninsular institutions.⁴ The dissemination of the new liturgy needed not only codices with the new rite,⁵ but also copies of St. Benedict's rule, which had replaced the traditional Visigothic monastic rules of St. Isidore and St. Fructuosus in the new annexed territories with Charlemagne's firm support.⁶ Moreover, the graphic and cultural impact of charters written in Caroline minuscule in the Frankish kingdom and arriving in the Spanish March under Frankish political control must also be considered.⁷ The direct cultural influence of Carolingian written production on what had been Visigothic soil naturally led to the gradual incorporation of graphic elements characteristic of Caroline minuscule by Visigothic script scribes and to the progressive change of graphic systems. After a quick process of graphic contamination, texts were already being written in the new script in major Septimanian and Catalan production centres in the first half of the ninth century.⁸ However, even within the Spanish March, as well as charters were still being written in Visigothic script in the late ninth century albeit mostly in secondary centres isolated from the main routes of cultural exchange, liturgical books preserving the Hispanic rite were produced in the tenth and eleventh centuries as some rituals point towards their use mixed with the new Office.⁹

In the north and north-western Iberian Peninsula, the trans-Pyrenean influence seen in the gradual adoption of the new rite and the new supranational handwriting can similarly be observed long before the Synods of Burgos and Leon and the first Iberian testimonies in the new script. While

⁴ See A. M. Mundó, "Importación, exportación y expoliaciones de códices en Cataluña," in *Coloquio sobre la circulación de códices y escritos en la Península y Europa en los siglos VIII-XIII, 16-19 septiembre 1982: Actas* (Santiago de Compostela, 1988), 87-134 (100-103). On the authors and texts known in the Catalan counties, see Id., "La cultura i els llibres," in *Història de Catalunya*, vol. 2 (Barcelona, 1978), 469-473, and J. Alturo Perucho, *Historia del llibre manuscrit a Catalunya* (Barcelona, 2003), 80-88.

⁵ See A. M. Mundó, "Un fragment molt antic de litúrgia romana a Catalunya," in *II Congrés litúrgic de Montserrat*, vol. 3 (Montserrat, 1966-67), 173-188 (Tarragona, Archivo Histórico Archidocesano, frag. 22,1, c. 890).

⁶ Mundó, "Importación, exportación y expoliaciones de códices en Cataluña," 103-104.

⁷ J. Alturo Perucho, "L'enseignement et l'apprentissage de l'écriture en Catalogne au Moyen Age," in *Teaching Writing: Learning to Write. Proceedings of the XVIth colloquium of the Comité International de Paléographie Latine*, ed. P. R. Robinson (London, 2010), 193-204.

⁸ On Pyrenean/Septimanian Visigothic script, see J. Alturo Perucho, "La escritura visigótica de origen transpirenaico. Una aproximación a sus particularidades," *Hispania Sacra* XLVI/93 (1994): 33-64 (56-67). Also A. M. Mundó, "El Commicus palimpsest Paris lat. 2269. Amb notes sobre litúrgia i manuscrits visigòtics a Septimània i Catalunya," in *Liturgica I. Cardinali I. A. Schuster in memoriam* (Montserrat, 1956), 151-275 (176). On the transition from Visigothic to Caroline in Catalonia, see J. Alturo Perucho, "Escritura visigótica y escritura carolina en el contexto cultural de la Cataluña del siglo IX," *Memoria Ecclesiae* 2 (1991): 33-44, 298; A. M. Mundó and J. Alturo Perucho, "Problemàtica de les scriptures del períodes de transició i de les marginals," in *Cultura Neolatina. Rivista di Filologia Romanza fondata da Giulio Bertoni*, LVIII 1/2 (1998), 121-148; Id., "La escritura de transición de la visigótica a la carolina en la Cataluña del siglo IX," in *Actas del VIII Coloquio del Comité Internacional de Paleografía Latina (Madrid-Toledo 1987)* (Madrid, 1990), 131-138; J. Alturo Perucho, "Tipus d'escritura a la Catalunya dels segles VIII-X," in *Catalunya a l'època carolíngia. Art i cultura abans del romànic (segles IX i X)* (Barcelona, 1999), 131-134, 485-487.

⁹ M. C. Díaz y Díaz, "La circulation des manuscrits dans la Péninsule Ibérique du VIIIe au XIe siècle," *Cahiers de Civilisation Médiévale* 12 (1969): 219-241 (240, footnotes 154 and 156). For example, the Sacramentary of the Cathedral of Vic (Vic, Arxiu del capbreu, ms. 66) and the Pontifical of Vic (Vic, Museo episcopal, Cod. 104). Paris, Bibliotheque Nationale de France, lat. 933, copied in the diocese of Carcassonne, shows how some Old Hispanic forms were still preserved in the late eleventh/early twelfth century in southern France (*Hispania Vetus. Musical-Liturgical manuscripts from Visigothic origins to the Franco-Roman transition (9th-12th centuries)*, cord. S. Zapke (Bilbao, 2007), 334). See also Reynolds, "The Visigothic Liturgy," for the influence of Old Hispanic forms in codices with the Roman liturgy written in the Carolingian Empire. On the codices kept in Catalan centres in the ninth century, see J. Alturo Perucho, "Les inventaires de livres en Catalogne du IX au XII siècles," *Scriptorium* L/2 (1996): 370-379.

the circulation of codices during the eighth and ninth centuries across the Christian centres in the north and the main Mozarabic centres and from peninsular centres to Europe was mostly focused on Hispanic literary production, in the late ninth and tenth centuries the direction of cultural interactions among intellectual hubs changed. The decline of fluid communication between the Christian nuclei of the north and those of the south of the peninsula was balanced by more frequent relations with the Frankish world.¹⁰ On the one hand, the religious pressure towards the Mozarabs in the south prevented the Mozarabic centres of continuing the pace of manuscript production of highly appreciated texts exported to the northern Spanish centres and to Europe developed so far, increasing the migration of intellectuals to the safer areas of north-western and north-eastern Iberia.¹¹ At the same time, the political measures of the Christian northern kingdoms regarding the integration of these people, and the efficient administration of the recently absorbed territories, favoured the more or less quiet scene that allowed the Frankish influence to grow. In the mid-ninth century, the Way of Saint James, linking all major northern cultural centres with Europe by land and sea, was already open, the routes secured by economic incentives adopted by the Leonese, Castilian, and Navarrese kings.¹² The Mozarabic production centres were no longer a pole of attraction and the path to new cultural interests, encouraged by the arrival of French scholars, was paved.¹³ In consequence, already in the early tenth century and increasingly as time progressed, references to the circulation of codices among the northern Christian nuclei not only show that traditional texts of peninsular heritage like those of Isidore, Leander, Taio, and Ildephonse or Gregorius Magnus, Venantius Fortunatus, and the *Vitae Patrum* were produced, but also show that texts from outside the peninsula, like the works of especially Smaragdus were thereafter copied and disseminated¹⁴ and not read only by a few intellectuals as it was the case before.¹⁵

The direct influence of these new texts, coming to the northern kingdoms especially from southern France but also from Catalonia, can be observed in different aspects of Astur-Leonese written testimonies before the change of graphic system.¹⁶ Since the early tenth century, scribes copying codices or writing charters in Visigothic script began to incorporate common Caroline minuscule

¹⁰ Díaz y Díaz, "La circulation des manuscrits," 219-241.

¹¹ Díaz y Díaz, "La circulation des manuscrits," 233-235.

¹² A. Rucquoi, "Cluny, el Camino Francés y la Reforma Gregoriana," *Medievalismo: Boletín de la Sociedad Española de Estudios Medievales* 20 (2010): 97-122 (101-105); Id., "Hospites seu Peregrini: Itinerarios de peregrinación en la alta Edad Media (850-1150)," *Iacobus* 29-30 (2011): 15-47; Id., "O caminho de Santiago: a criação de um itinerário," *Signum* 9 (2007): 95-120.

¹³ J. Mattoso ("Condições económicas e sociais da circulação de códices na península Ibérica," in *Coloquio sobre la circulación de códices y escritos en la Península y Europa* (Santiago de Compostela, 1982), 135-155) studies the relationship between the social and economic conditions of production centers and the adoption of or openness to cultural changes in northern Iberia in the eight to twelfth centuries. See also Barton, "Spain in the Eleventh Century," 175-177.

¹⁴ As an example: Córdoba, Archivo Capitular, ms. 1 Smaragdus, *Liber Homiliarum* c. 953-960, copied at the monastery of Valeránica (Burgos). A list of extant codices copied in Visigothic script is available in A. Millares Carlo, *Corpus de códices visigóticos* (Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, 1999). An online summary is available in A. Castro Correa, "Visigothic script timeline. Online Catalog of Visigothic script manuscripts," *Littera Visigothica* (2013-2015), <litteravisigothica.com/visigothic-script-timeline>.

¹⁵ Mattoso, "Condições económicas e sociais da circulação de codices," 143; M. C. Díaz y Díaz, "Textos altomedievales extrahispanos en la Península," in *Coloquio sobre la circulación de códices y escritos en la Península y Europa* (Santiago de Compostela, 1982), 239-265; Díaz y Díaz, "La circulation des manuscrits," 236-240.

¹⁶ M^a C. del Camino Martínez, "La escritura carolina en la Península Ibérica," in *Paleografía I: La escritura en España hasta 1250. Actas de las IV Jornadas de la Sociedad Española de Ciencias y Técnicas Historiográficas* (Burgos, 2008), 119-140 (130); A. Millares Carlo, *Tratado de Paleografía Española*, 3d ed. (Madrid, 1983), 140-143.

abbreviations into their manuscripts, like, for example, the Tironian note for *con*, the simplified form of *episcopus* as *eps* or that of the possessives *noster/uester* with theme in *r* instead of in *s*. In the same way, some codicological similarities between Castilian and French codices have been pointed out, like the pricking and ruling of the page before copying the text and the structure of the colophons added to the first Castilian examples, comparable to those of French books from the Carolingian period.¹⁷ Also in some codices, the change in the style of illumination and in musical notation appears to be indebted to early contacts with French, especially Aquitanian, models.¹⁸ This evident interaction between graphic testimonies from both sides of the Pyrenees continued to grow during the first half of the eleventh century despite the political instability of the northern kingdoms.¹⁹ The wealth of new texts, particularly codices arranged according to the Roman rite, increased.²⁰

Traditional scholarship has given the Navarrese kings a special role in welcoming the liturgical change due to their close relation with the Burgundian abbey of Cluny.²¹ Sancho III of Navarre's interest in introducing the monastic reform in his kingdom, which has been erroneously thought to have been continued by his son Fernando of Castile after his death,²² was a clear first pole of attraction. Around 1025, Sancho requested the help of Abbot Odilo of Cluny in introducing the Benedictine reform in the monasteries of his kingdom. In order to promote the change, Sancho sent a group of monks to study at Cluny, who, on their return, joined the community at the monastery of San Juan de la Peña. However, though this early Cluniac presence in northern Iberia could have influenced other Navarrese, Castilian, and Leonese centres to adopt liturgical change, it did not.²³ Cluniac influence expanded slowly and with Sancho's death in 1035, the favour for Cluny seems to have declined, despite the requests made by Abbot Odilo to Sancho's heirs. When Fernando, Count of Castile and soon after King of Leon-Castile by his marriage with Sancha, presided over the councils of Coyanza in 1055 and of Compostela in 1056, church reform with adoption of liturgical influences from beyond the Pyrenees was encouraged but still according to a proper observance of the Old Hispanic liturgy.²⁴

¹⁷ J. Pérez de Urbel, "El Antifonario de León. El escritor y la época," *Archivos Leoneses* 8 (1954): 115-144.

¹⁸ J. Williams, *Early Spanish manuscript illumination* (New York, 1977), 19-20, 21-24 ('decorated initials became decidedly Carolingian in style'). See also F. Galván Freile, "El *Liber canticorum et horarum* de Sancha (B.G.U.S., Ms. 2668). Entre la tradición prerrománica y la modernidad," in *Hispaniens Norden im 11. Jahrhundert: christliche Kunst im Umbruch* (Petersberg, 2009), 248-256; S. Boynton, *Silent Music. Medieval Song and the Construction of History in Eighteenth-Century Spain* (New York, 2011), 5; E. Klinka, "Ego misera et peccatrix...: El *Liber mozarabicus canticorum et horarum* (Salamanca, ms. 2668)," *e-Spania* 13 (2012) <e-spania.revues.org/21044> (for a synthesis); *Hispania Vetus*, 372-373.

¹⁹ This political-administrative instability was a result of, mainly, confrontation between kings and nobles, difficult successions and border adjustments, and weakness against the Muslims. See Barton, "Spain in the Eleventh Century," 154-190.

²⁰ Some extant manuscripts, copies of Caroline minuscule models in Visigothic script, include: Cambridge, University Library, Add. Ms. 5905 (two fragments of a *Breviarium*) (Millares Carlo, *Corpus de códices visigóticos*, nº 32); Reading, University Library – formerly Sheffield, Ruskin museum, 7 – (Paulus Diaconus, *Homiliarium*) (Millares Carlo, *Corpus de códices visigóticos*, nº 273).

²¹ C. Bishko, "Fernando I and the origins of the Leonese-Castilian alliance with Cluny," *Cuadernos de Historia de España* 47 (1968): 31-135 and 48 (1969): 30-116.

²² For a reconsideration of the relationship between Fernando I, Alfonso VI, and Cluny, see L. Pick, "Rethinking Cluny in Spain," *Journal of Medieval Iberian Studies* 5/1 (2013): 1-17.

²³ Barton, "Spain in the Eleventh Century," 177; Walker, *Views of Transition*, 24.

²⁴ "The idea of abandoning the old liturgy for some alien French version unintelligibly pronounced was not likely to attract Fernando I" (R. Wright, *Late Latin and Early Romance in Spain and Carolingian France* (Liverpool, 1982), 208-209). See also Klinka, "Ego misera et peccatrix," §5; Pick, "Rethinking Cluny in Spain," 5-7, 11 (which analyses the adaptation of this external influence through the prayer books of Fernando I and Sancha, and their daughter Urraca (Santiago de Compostela, Biblioteca Universitaria, ms. 609; Salamanca, Biblioteca

The cultural exchange and liturgical influence, which had until then been part of the natural interaction of neighbouring kingdoms, would, in the second half of the century, no longer be incidental. The external pressure to adopt the Roman liturgy and Caroline minuscule script in the northern peninsular kingdoms was strategically politicised during the reign of Fernando and Sancha's son Alfonso VI.²⁵ King of Leon, Castile, and Galicia after dethroning his brothers in 1072,²⁶ Alfonso quickly realised the benefits that open borders to Europe could offer to his kingdom. His reign saw territorial expansion against both the other Christian realms and the Muslims, administrative reorganisation, and social and economic growth that reflect a clear and conscious policy to make his kingdom the dominant realm in the peninsula by taking advantage of the new possibilities opened up by the changing world around him.²⁷ During his rule, the Way of Saint James was fully established thanks to increased security measures, construction of hospital facilities and accommodation for the pilgrims, churches, structural improvements, and tax exemptions.²⁸ The continuous flow of foreign visitors, churchmen, merchants, and artisans to Santiago de Compostela not only stimulated urban development along the route but also left a profound cultural imprint opening the peninsula to Europe as never before. The establishment of political alliances with geographical entities that could help Alfonso strengthen his power, not only in peninsular territory but also abroad, was a priority directly manifested in his, and his daughters', marriages as well as in the resumption of warm relations between the kingdom and Cluny.

The imperial ambitions of Alfonso VI clearly confronted those of Pope Gregory VII, who, by advocating liturgical unification, sought to establish Rome's dominance over not only the Hispanic Church but also all the peninsular Christian kingdoms. The introduction of the Roman liturgy also meant the acceptance of Roman canon law, limiting the royal power perpetuated by the Visigothic tradition over ecclesiastical matters.²⁹ The first attempts at reform of a church allegedly tainted with Priscilianism, Arianism, and Saracen heretic features had been made, without much success, by Charlemagne in the Adoptionism controversy.³⁰ Since then, the situation had changed. Alexander II, Gregory's predecessor, and his papal legate Hugh Candidus had had success in the kingdom of Aragon not long before Alfonso's rule. San Juan de la Peña adopted the Roman rite in 1071, as did so the rest of Aragon in 1074. Finally, when the kingdom of Navarre was absorbed by Aragon in c. 1076, the liturgical change was adopted there too by merging both churches.³¹ Thereafter, codices with the new

Universitaria, ms. 2668 – see A. Castro Correa, “Codex of the month (VII): Santiago, BU, ms 609,” *Littera Visigothica* (April 2015), <http://litteravisigothica.com/codex-of-the-month-vii-santiago-bu-ms-609/>).

²⁵ J. P. Rubio Sadia, *Las órdenes religiosas y la introducción del Rito Romano en la Iglesia de Toledo. Una aportación desde las fuentes litúrgicas* (Toledo, 2004), 173.

²⁶ Barton, “Spain in the Eleventh Century,” 167-169.

²⁷ *Santiago, Saint-Denis, and Saint Peter: the reception of the Roman liturgy in Leon-Castile in 1080*, coord. B. Reilly (New York, 1985), ix-xi. See also B. Reilly, *The Kingdom of Leon-Castilla under King Alfonso VI, 1065–1109* (Princeton, 1988), and J. M^a Mínguez Fernández, *Alfonso VI: poder, expansión y reorganización interior* (Hondarribia, 2000) as general background.

²⁸ Rucquoi, “Cluny, el Camino Francés y la Reforma Gregoriana,” 104-105; Id., “Hospites seu Peregrini,” 15-47; Id., “Santiago de Compostela y Europa; ¿intercambios? ¿Identidad?,” in *Identidad europea e intercambios culturales en el Camino de Santiago (siglos XI-XV)* (Santiago, 2013), 27-49.

²⁹ See L. Vones, “The Substitution of the Hispanic Liturgy by the Roman Rite in the Kingdoms of the Iberian Peninsula,” in *Hispania Vetus. Musical-Liturgical manuscripts from Visigothic origins to the Franco-Roman transition (9th-12th centuries)* (Bilbao, 2007), 43-60 (49-50, 52); Rucquoi, “Cluny, el Camino Francés y la Reforma Gregoriana,” 106, 121-122.

³⁰ See Reynolds, “The Visigothic Liturgy,” 919-920; Walker, *Views of Transition*, 25-27.

³¹ Vones, “The Substitution,” 46-47.

rite produced in French centres were directly imported into the Aragonese see,³² even though there would be still vestiges of the Old rite (and script) as late as in the late twelfth century.³³

In contrast with the situation in Aragon, the new liturgy had not yet been formally introduced in Leon-Castile by the 1070s. There has recently been discussion about how Alfonso could have benefited from the bond his sisters, particularly Urraca Fernández, and his second wife, Constance of Burgundy, had with the Abbey of Cluny, using Abbot Hugh of Cluny, Constance's uncle, as an intermediary in the introduction of the reform in the northern peninsula.³⁴ Such an alliance would have been strategically valuable for both sides: Alfonso VI was in need of allies against Rome and the kingdom of Aragon, whereas Cluny, striving for liturgical unification albeit less aggressively than the Pope, sought to expand its own influence and not Rome's over the peninsula. Gregory's desire for reform adopting the Roman rite was difficult to avoid, and Alfonso VI seems to never have been, at least openly, against the liturgical change. The self-proclaimed *Imperator totius Hispaniae* neither wanted to submit to the Pope notwithstanding.³⁵ The acceptance of liturgical unification could help in placing Leon-Castile in the European orbit on par with the other members of Christendom as a reformed medieval kingdom,³⁶ but Alfonso seemed unwilling to relinquish power in the process. As a result, Alfonso let Cluny, far more tolerant than the Pope, and not Rome, take the role of introducing the change.³⁷

Between 1073 and 1077, Alfonso VI transferred four monasteries of his kingdom to the Burgundian house, among them the royal abbey of Sahagún, which were thereafter centres of the dissemination of the reform program.³⁸ Gradually, the continued cultural pressure, Alfonso's clear tendency to favour the openness of the kingdom, the arrival of Cluniac monks, the Pope's perseverance and the

³² Huesca, Archivo de la Catedral, Cod. 1, copied in Saint Pierre of Moissac in the second half of the eleventh century (*Hispania Vetus*, 354).

³³ As attested by the Antiphonary of Santa Cruz de la Serós (Jaca) and the Breviary of San Juan de la Peña, now in El Escorial, Biblioteca del Monasterio, ms. L.III.3 (*Hispania Vetus*, 362-365). Visigothic script prevailed, however, in Navarre until the mid-twelfth century, with the last charter written in Visigothic script dating 1162. See A. Ubieto Arteta, "Con qué tipo de letra se escribió en Navarra hace mil años," *Revista de Archivos, Bibliotecas y Museos* LXIII/2 (1957): 409-422 (422); A. Canellas López, "Paleografía aragonesa de la Alta Edad Media anterior al año 1137," *Anuario de Estudios Medievales* 21 (1991): 471-492.

³⁴ Pick, "Rethinking Cluny in Spain," 11-13. On Cluny in Spain, see C. M. Reglero de la Fuente, *Cluny en España: los prioratos de la provincia y sus redes sociales (1073-ca.1270)* (León, 2008).

³⁵ Reilly, *The Kingdom of León-Castilla under Alfonso VI*, 103; Rucquoi, "Cluny, el Camino Francés y la Reforma Gregoriana," 122.

³⁶ Rubio Sandia, *Las órdenes religiosas y la introducción del Rito Romano*, 50.

³⁷ Wright, *Late Latin and Early Romance*, 210, 211; Walker, *Views of Transition*, 31, 35. Pick ("Rethinking Cluny in Spain," 13-14) argues that, in order to justify relations between the king of Leon-Castile and the abbey and give them precedence over Gregory's claims based upon Constantine's donation, Alfonso VI and Abbot Hugh of Cluny consciously rewrote the past. They assigned to Fernando I a continuous relation with Cluny after Sancho III's death, materialised in an annual donation of 1,000 gold pieces that, according to the evidence, more than likely never existed. They also seem to have agreed the supposed intercession of Hugh in the liberation of Alfonso when his brother, Sancho II of Castile, made him prisoner in Burgos in 1072. See also Rucquoi, "Cluny, el Camino Francés y la Reforma Gregoriana," 119; J. Montenegro, "El cambio de rito en los reinos de León y Castilla según las crónicas: la memoria, la distorsión y el olvido," in *La construcción medieval de la memoria regia*, ed. P. Martínez Sopena and A. Rodríguez (Valencia, 2011), 71-86 (84-85).

³⁸ Visigothic script prevailed in Sahagún for some fifty years more despite de adoption of the new rite (see note 125), which may be explained by the prominence of the scriptorium, whose scribes were reluctant to abandon the graphic system they had mastered.

effectiveness of his papal legates, notably Cardinal Richard of St. Victor of Marseilles,³⁹ were to result in the acceptance of the new rite. Not long after of the new script at least for copying liturgical texts.

In the Council of Burgos in 1080 the Hispanic liturgy was formally abandoned and the Roman rite introduced, nevertheless the unification of the Western Church was not achieved as Gregory VII wanted. As happened in Septimania and Catalonia, the adoption of the new rite in Aragon, Navarre, and Leon-Castile could not have been effective in all urban and rural ecclesiastical institutions in the same way. It proceeded slowly and gradually, even if one considers only the need of providing codices with the new liturgy and leaves aside all possible reactions against the change that undoubtedly arose.⁴⁰ Indeed, before the Synod of 1080, the reform had detractors even in such traditional Cluniac centres as Sahagún, whose abbot appointed directly by Alfonso VI seems to have come out in support of the Hispanic liturgy.⁴¹ Around the time of the synod, notable resistance seems to have arisen too in major monasteries such as Santo Domingo de Silos, whose attachment to the old tradition is shown by three extant manuscripts copied following the Roman rite albeit in Visigothic script and with Mozarabic neumes,⁴² and San Millán de la Cogolla, which produced manuscripts in defence of the Hispanic liturgy⁴³ continuing Old Hispanic forms and Visigothic script.⁴⁴ Even some cathedral centres were, at least initially, against the change.⁴⁵ Notwithstanding this, the synod of 1080 officially marks the beginning of the gradual process of adoption of new liturgical forms for, despite opposition, changes were made that affected the celebration of the Mass and the observance of the cathedral and monastic Offices.⁴⁶

In contrast with Gregory VII's globalising aim, it must also be considered that the decrees agreed upon at the synod were only intended to affect the Christian kingdoms and not the territories under Muslim rule where the Mozarabic communities were numerous.⁴⁷ As Alfonso VI's effective military campaigns continued to expand Leon-Castile's borders, territories in which the Hispanic liturgy had been preserved were progressively recovered. Thus, although the decisions adopted at the Council of Burgos were still in force, in practice, both liturgies seem to have coexisted since enforcing a change of rites was not conducive to Alfonso's intentions as emperor, which were to assimilate the new territories and their people as quickly and efficiently as possible and with minimal confrontation.⁴⁸ Toledo, recovered in 1085, is a significant example of a city where the Old rite was, and is even today, still practised.⁴⁹

³⁹ See Rucquoi, "Cluny, el Camino Francés y la Reforma Gregoriana," on Cardinal Richard of St Victor of Marseilles.

⁴⁰ Walker, *Views of Transition*, 30-34.

⁴¹ Barton, "Spain in the Eleventh Century," 179-180; Vones, "The Substitution," 50-51. See also note 38.

⁴² London, British Library, Add. 30847, 30848, 30850. See A. Castro Correa, "The scribes of the Silos' Apocalypse (London, British Library, Add. MS 11695) and the scriptorium of Silos in the late eleventh century" (under review).

⁴³ El Escorial, Biblioteca del Monasterio, ms. d. I and Madrid, Real Academia de la Historia, Em. 22.

⁴⁴ Madrid, Real Academia de la Historia, Em. 52 and Em. 18.

⁴⁵ E.g. Toledo (Montenegro, "El cambio de rito," 79-80). See also note 49.

⁴⁶ Walker, *Views of Transition*, chapters 2 and 5; Mundó, "Importación, exportación y expoliaciones," 103-104.

⁴⁷ R. González Ruiz, "The persistence of the Mozarabic Liturgy in Toledo after AD 1080," in *Santiago, Saint-Denis, and Saint Peter: The Reception of the Roman Liturgy in León-Castille in 1080* (New York, 1985), 157-185 (163).

⁴⁸ Vones, "The Substitution," 51-52. See also Reynolds, "The Visigothic Liturgy," 945.

⁴⁹ Boynton, *Silent Music*, 7-14. Visigothic script had too a long life in the Mozarabic communities. On the characteristics of the Mozarabic Visigothic script and its extant manuscript sources, see E. Rodríguez Díaz, "Los manuscritos mozárabes: una encrucijada de culturas," in *Die Mozaraber. Definitionen und Perspektiven der Forschung* (Münster, 2011), 10-30; M^a C. del Camino Martínez, "La escritura visigótica de los centros mozárabes en su período primitivo," in *La escritura visigótica en la Península Ibérica: nuevas aportaciones*, ed. J. Alturo, A.

When Gregory VII died in 1085, and the aggressive ambitions of liturgical unification faded, Alfonso VI no longer saw the purpose of maintaining a close alliance with Cluny.⁵⁰ In consequence, although the Cluniac Bernard of Sédillac, former Abbot of Sahagún, was elevated to Archbishop of Toledo in 1086 and primate of the whole Hispanic Church in 1088,⁵¹ and thereafter Cluniac monks were granted episcopal and abbatial sees,⁵² the abbey's relations with the Leonese-Castilian kingdom were weakened, and its influence on Iberian soil diminished, or, at least, it seems had shifted to the north-western peninsula as will be discussed.

In parallel with the introduction of the Roman rite came the gradual replacement of writing systems, from Visigothic script to Caroline minuscule, favoured by the constant affluence of Caroline minuscule texts and foreign scholars, increased and consolidated by the acceptance of liturgical reform already examined. However, these texts continued to be copied mostly in Visigothic script.⁵³ Around 1090, another synod seems to have been held in Leon to discuss graphic unification for, at least, liturgical texts; clerics needed not only to learn the new script, alphabet, and abbreviation system, and improve their knowledge of medieval Latin, but also to master them in order to be able to read, understand, and, eventually, copy Roman texts correctly.⁵⁴ Although the proceedings of this new synod have not been preserved and the only extant references to their contents come from later scholars such as Lucas de Tuy, Jiménez de Rada, or Alfonso X,⁵⁵ this council cannot be thought of as a point of no return after which manuscripts in Visigothic script were no longer copied.⁵⁶ The effect of the Leon synod was as relative as that of the Synod of Burgos as is clearly indicated by the existence of codices of the Roman liturgy still copied in Visigothic script in the late eleventh and the twelfth centuries.⁵⁷ By examining the change of graphic systems through charters, a more reliable source

Castro, and M. Torras (Barcelona, 2012), 115-144; M. C. Díaz y Díaz, *Manuscritos visigóticos del sur de la Península: ensayo de distribución regional* (Sevilla, 1995). On the cultural context of these manuscripts, see C. Aillet, *Les mozarabes. Christianisme, islamisation et arabisation en Péninsule Ibérique (IXe-XIIIe siècle)* (Madrid, 2010), especially 7, 136.

⁵⁰ Rucquoi, "Cluny, el Camino Francés y la Reforma Gregoriana," 119.

⁵¹ Barton, "Spain in the Eleventh Century," 177-178. With Bernard of Sédillac came codices with the new rite, such as the Antiphonary now Toledo, Biblioteca Capitular, 44-1 (*Hispania Vetus*, 400-401).

⁵² Dalmacius was made Bishop of Santiago de Compostela (1094); Geraldus, former *chantor* of the Cathedral of Toledo, called from Moissac by Bernard, Bishop of Braga (1095); Mauricio, Bishop of Coimbra (c. 1098) and future Antipope Gregory VIII. See *Santiago, Saint-Denis, and Saint Peter*, xi; R. Fletcher, *The Episcopate in the Kingdom of León in the Twelfth Century* (Oxford, 1978), 37-38, 77-79.

⁵³ Madrid, Real Academia de la Historia, Cód. 18, *Missale* with the Roman rite in Visigothic script copied in San Millán de la Cogolla in the late eleventh century. On the other hand, London, British Library, Add. 30849, *Breviarium* of the Roman liturgy, was copied in Caroline minuscule around the same time, in or within the region of the Abbey of Silos (see J. Vezin, "El Códice British Library add. 30849 y la introducción de la Carolina en España," in *Silos. Un milenio. Actas del Congreso Internacional sobre la Abadía de Santo Domingo de Silos*, vol. 2 (Silos, 2003), 211-222). Another example is Madrid, Biblioteca Nacional, Vitr. 20-8, known as 'Missal of San Facundo', copied in Sahagún also in Caroline (see Walker, *Views of Transition*, 141 (chapter 4)).

⁵⁴ Wright, *Late Latin and Early Romance*, 234-235. See also J. Alturo Perucho, "El conocimiento del latín en la Cataluña del siglo IX: un capítulo de su historia cultural," *Euphrosyne* XXI (1993): 301-318.

⁵⁵ Lucas de Tuy, *Lucae Tudensis Chronicon Mundi (Corpus Christianorum: Continuatio Mediaevalis LXXIV)*, ed. E. Falque Rey (Turnhout, 2003), 305; *Historia de rebus Hispaniae (Corpus Christianorum: Continuatio Mediaevalis LXXII)*, ed. J. Fernández Valverde (Turnhout, 1987), lib. VI, cap. XXVIII, 213-214; *Primera crónica general de España que mandó componer Alfonso el Sabio y se continuaba bajo Sancho IV en 1289*, ed. R. Menéndez Pidal (Madrid, 1955), vol. II, 547.

⁵⁶ E. Terreros, *Paleografía Española...* (Madrid, 1758), 106-107. See also Camino Martínez, "La escritura Carolina en la Península Ibérica," 119-140 (126-127); Millares, *Tratado*, 142-143, 167; J. A. Fernández Flórez, *La elaboración de los documentos en los reinos hispánicos occidentales (ss. VI-XIII)* (Burgos, 2002), 128.

⁵⁷ Some examples: late eleventh century: see note 53, also León, Archivo Histórico Provincial, fragm. II *Missale* (Leonese area); late eleventh/early twelfth: Braga, Arquivo Distrital, Coleção Cronológica, 280,3 *Antiphonarium*

than codices with which to ponder how the practical introduction of Caroline minuscule must have occurred for they tend to provide specific dates for each written example, it can be clearly seen how little influence the Synods directly had in everyday manuscript production. The first charters written in the foreign graphic model in north-western Iberia are dated to the early twelfth century, between 1110 and 1120 depending on the area,⁵⁸ while the latest examples of charters written in Visigothic script date from 1166 (Asturias)⁵⁹ and 1172 (Portugal).⁶⁰ The process of graphic change was thus rather slow, but, as shown by highlighting the data provided by the extant sources from Galicia that will be discussed, not as slow as it could have been.

In conclusion, the adoption of new rite and script was not a direct imposition but the result of a confluence of far-reaching historical and cultural factors. It took place progressively, dependent on the specific circumstances of each geographical area, and even of each production centre as can clearly be seen in the analysis of the script used in the royal chancellery.⁶¹ As scribes were appointed royal notaries from different centres throughout the kingdom, some versed in Visigothic, some in Caroline minuscule, and some in a script and style influenced by both, they continued to use their own scripts in service of the monarchy,⁶² a situation that emphasises the importance of the learning process and the development of schools in ecclesiastical centres⁶³ and by extension the study of regional variants and different cultural and political contexts.

(copied in Braga diocese), Coimbra, Arquivo Universitário, s/n *Missale* and *Antiphonarium* (near Coimbra), Coimbra, Arquivo Universitário, IV-3^a S-Gv. 44 *Antiphonarium* (monastery of Friestas); early twelfth: Toledo, Archivo y Biblioteca Capitular, 10.5 *Antiphonarium* (copied in or near Toledo), Santiago de Compostela, Archivo de la Catedral, fragm. 1 *Missale* (probably copied in Santiago de Compostela). The last codex copied in Visigothic script is a *Misticus* from nearby Toledo (Madrid, Biblioteca Nacional, mss. 10110) dated c. 1300 (Millares Carlo, *Corpus de códices visigóticos*, n^o 173).

⁵⁸ On the chronology of the transition from Visigothic script to Caroline minuscule in north-western Iberia see A. Castro Correa, "Visigothic script versus Caroline minuscule: The collision of two cultural worlds in twelfth-century Galicia" (LMS diss., Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies, 2015), and A. Castro Correa, "Leaving the past behind, adapting to the future: the last survivors of Visigothic script in the Iberian Peninsula" (under elaboration).

⁵⁹ M. Calleja Puerta, "De la visigótica a la carolina en los documentos del Archivo de San Vicente de Oviedo: la escritura de *Dominicus y Pelagius*," in *Actas de las IV Jornadas de la Sociedad Española de Ciencias y Técnicas Historiográficas* (Burgos, 2008), 189-200.

⁶⁰ M^a J. Azevedo Santos, *Da visigótica à carolina. A escrita em Portugal de 882 a 1172 : aspectos técnicos e culturais* (Lisboa, 1994); Id., "La caroline au Portugal: une écriture d'importation," in *Régionalisme et internationalisme: problèmes de paléographie et de codicologie du Moyen Âge. Actes du XV^e Colloque du Comité international de paléographie latine (Vienne, 13-17 septembre 2005)*, ed. O. Krestens and F. Lackner (Viena, 2007), 81-86.

⁶¹ Charters from Alfonso VI's chancellery were copied mostly in Visigothic script, those of his successor Urraca vary between both scripts (usually Visigothic for Galician charters and Caroline for Leonese-Castilian ones), and Caroline was predominant under Alfonso VII but still bearing Visigothic remnants (J. Muñoz y Rivero, *Paleografía visigoda: método teórico-práctico para aprender a leer los codices y documentos españoles de los siglos V al XII* (Madrid, 1881), 36).

⁶² It would be interesting to analyse whether the choice of one script or another in the royal chancellery had anything to do with the beneficiary or addressee of the document and his cultural-political affiliations or interests as the extant textual evidence seems to suggest. See J. M. Ruiz Asencio, "Cronología de la desaparición de la escritura visigótica en los documentos de León y Castilla," in *Actas de las IV Jornadas de la Sociedad Española de Ciencias y Técnicas Historiográficas* (Burgos, 2008), 93-117 (98).

⁶³ As has been already pointed out by Camino Martínez ("La escritura Carolina en la Península Ibérica," 128).

3. The transition from Visigothic script to Caroline minuscule in Galicia

3.1. Galicia, Alfonso VI, and the introduction of the new rite

How did the historical context outlined in the preceding section affect the westernmost area of the Iberian Peninsula, the kingdom of Galicia? When Sancho III of Navarre, the king who had opened the path to Cluniac influence into the northern Christian realms, died in 1035, Vermudo III of Leon saw an opportunity to recover the territories that Sancho had left to one of his sons, Fernando, Count of Castile and husband of Vermudo's sister Sancha. His ambition, however, led him to failure, defeated and killed by Fernando, who became King of Leon and Castile after 1037. The new king focused his attention on consolidating his authority over his new kingdom and, from the sources preserved, it can be established that the change of dynasty, from Astur to Navarre and from Vermudo III to Fernando I, was well received by the nobility and the main ecclesiastical magnates in Leon.⁶⁴ In Galicia, on the other hand, the situation was rather different, making the assimilation of the northwest into the Leonese-Castilian kingdom challenging, to say the least. The local nobility acted openly against supporting changes forced by a centralised power that could jeopardise their control over Galicia, making essential for the new king, as it would be for his successor, to establish secure control over the outbreaks associated with foreign supporters and to create their own new nobility.⁶⁵ It was also crucial to win allies within the Church, since controlling the main ecclesiastical *señoríos* of Galicia would provide stable nuclei of power upon which to structure the progressive territorial reorganisation and assimilation of Galicia into the crown. Alfonso VI, Fernando's heir, continued the process started by his father, and even went further, seemingly taking the matter into his own hands. It has been mentioned that Alfonso VI rebuilt relations with Cluny in order to appease the reforming aspirations of Gregory VII. In the same way, he made use of his control over ecclesiastical affairs to elect bishops favourable to his cause to fill the Galician sees. When he needed political allies to ensure his self-proclaimed imperial power over all Spains, he knew where to find them and, if suitable supporters were not available, how to establish them.

In Lugo, around 1086, Alfonso VI needed to deal with the revolt led by Count Rodrigo Ovéquiz and his supporter the Bishop of Compostela Diego Peláez while the see of Lugo was vacant.⁶⁶ Rodrigo was captured and sent to prison; Bishop Diego was arrested and forced to resign, accepted voluntarily exile to Aragon, where Pedro I, Alfonso's enemy, welcomed him. The clear resentment of the Galician nobility evident in Rodrigo's revolt forced Alfonso to intervene by ousting the local nobility through imposing his daughter's Urraca husband, Raymond of Burgundy, brother of Pope Callixtus II, as Count of Galicia in 1087. Raymond was well received, possibly because the local nobility was no longer strong enough to fight against him, and quickly found an ally in one of the most important Galician noble houses left, the counts of Traba, who would thereafter be tutors of the Leonese-Castilian kings.⁶⁷ Once the nobility was under control, Alfonso focused his attention on

⁶⁴ Barton, "Spain in the Eleventh Century," 163-164; Reilly, *The Kingdom of León-Castilla under Alfonso VI*, 7-8.

⁶⁵ On the Galician nobility, the foundations of its power, and its relation with the monarchy, see M^a C. Pallares Méndez and E. Portela Silva, *Galicia na época medieval* (A Coruña, 1991), 80-103. As for the political implications of the change of dynasty, see R. Fletcher, *Saint James's Catapult: The Life and Times of Diego Gelmírez of Santiago de Compostela* (New York, 1984), chapter 2.

⁶⁶ Fletcher, *Saint James's Catapult*, 32; Reilly, *The Kingdom of León-Castilla under Alfonso VI*, 195-197 and footnote 30; M. Mosquera Agrelo, "La diócesis de Lugo en la Edad Media", in *Historia de las diócesis españolas*, vol. 15. Iglesias de Lugo, Mondoñedo-Ferrol y Orense, coord. J. García Oro (Madrid, 2002), 31-35; A. de Abel Vilela, *La ciudad de Lugo en los siglos XII al XV. Urbanismo y sociedad* (A Coruña, 2010), 63-64, 494-497.

⁶⁷ J. L. López Sangil, *A nobreza altomedieval galega* (Noia, 2005); A. López Ferreiro, *Don Alfonso VII, rei de Galicia e o seu aio o conde de Traba* (Noia, 2006); Barton, "Spain in the Eleventh Century," 180. Alfonso VI also married his other daughter, Teresa, to a foreigner: Henry of Burgundy, Constance's nephew and Raymond of Burgundy's

establishing trustworthy allies, favourable to his political strategy, in the major Galician ecclesiastical centres.⁶⁸

In 1088, in all likelihood with Archbishop Bernard of Toledo's support, Alfonso VI promoted Bishop Amor to the see of Lugo. Nothing is known about Bishop Amor's background, although his unusual name has been thought to indicate a foreign origin.⁶⁹ The close alliance between Amor and the king allowed the see to prosper in what was one of its worst moments for it had recently lost not only territories but also political and ecclesiastical pre-eminence with the restoration of the sees of Braga and Orense some twenty years before.⁷⁰ Already in 1088, Alfonso VI granted Bishop Amor lordship over the town, strengthening episcopal authority, protecting capitular property, and regulating markets, while Amor, in return, engineered reforms within the ecclesiastical administration of the diocese to reassert control over diocesan territories, as the king desired.⁷¹ Bishop Amor reorganised the cathedral chapter of Lugo, located in nearby Fingoy, and he may also have been the one who introduced the new rite into the diocese, or at least gladly welcomed manuscripts containing its liturgy, although there is no direct evidence on this point.⁷² When Amor died in 1095, the Cluniac Geraldus, former *cantor* of the Cathedral of Toledo, was appointed bishop of the recently restored metropolitan see of Braga, which must have given strength to the introduction of the new rite to all its suffragan Galician dioceses, among them Lugo.⁷³

The early twelfth century, under Alfonso VI's successor Queen Urraca, was once again a difficult period for the diocese of Lugo.⁷⁴ Under a weak bishop, Pedro II,⁷⁵ the see allied itself with Alfonso el Batallador in the civil war, and thus against the future King Alfonso VII and the see of Santiago de Compostela, where Bishop Diego Xelmírez was named, in addition to being archbishop, the head of the royal chancellery in around 1127.⁷⁶ But despite this unfortunate period of political instability, Lugo managed to re-establish its importance as the traditional Roman and Visigothic centre it was and earn back the royal favour. Changes towards liturgical and graphical unification continued with Bishop Pedro III, a former chaplain of Queen Urraca, promoted by the Queen, the Bishop of Santiago de Compostela, and Archbishop Bernard of Toledo.⁷⁷ Under the supervision of the see of Santiago, Pedro III introduced further improvements within the cathedral chapter by advocating the Gregorian Reform. He was also active in acquiring endowments for his see and started to build a new cathedral

cousin. He would be rewarded with the title Count of Portugal in 1095, and Henry and Teresa's son would be the first king of Portugal, Afonso Henriques.

⁶⁸ Rucquoi, "Cluny, el Camino Francés y la Reforma Gregoriana," 122.

⁶⁹ Fletcher, *Saint James's Catapult*, 43-47 (episcopal appointments in Galicia made by García and Alfonso VI).

⁷⁰ A. Almeida e Cunha, *A Chancelaria Arquiepiscopal de Braga (1071-1244)* (Noia, 2005), 47; Mosquera Agrelo, "La diócesis de Lugo," 388-389.

⁷¹ Mosquera Agrelo, "La diócesis de Lugo," 33-35.

⁷² On the evolution of the cathedral chapter of Lugo, see Mosquera Agrelo, "La diócesis de Lugo," 27-29, 43-44; Abel Vilela, *La ciudad de Lugo*, 157-163, 419 et seqq.; J. D'Emilio, "The Cathedral Chapter of Lugo in the Twelfth and Thirteenth Centuries: Reform and Retrenchment," in *Cross, Crescent, and Conversion: Studies on Medieval Spain and Christendom in Memory of Richard Fletcher*, ed. S. Barton and P. Linehan (Leiden, 2008), 193-226 (198-205).

⁷³ Mattoso, "Condições económicas e sociais da circulação de códices," 148.

⁷⁴ *Historia Compostelana*, 175, 230-232.

⁷⁵ Pedro II would resign as Bishop of Lugo at the Council of Palencia in 1113. Pallares and Portela, *Galicia na época medieval*, 323-324; Mosquera Agrelo, "La diócesis de Lugo," 37-40; Abel Vilela, *La ciudad de Lugo*, 498-501.

⁷⁶ M. Lucas Álvarez, *El Reino de León en la Alta Edad Media: Las cancellerías reales (1109-1230)*, vol. 5 (León, 1993), 332-336, 349-399.

⁷⁷ A. García Conde and A. López Valcárcel, *Episcopologio lucense* (Lugo, 1991), 166-183; Mosquera Agrelo, "La diócesis de Lugo," 39-40.

while maintaining close relations with the papacy.⁷⁸ In 1118, Pedro III appointed a certain Bernardo as prior of the canons, a foreigner thought to have been chosen specifically to manage the transition, and soon after, in 1122, he chose Pelayo as episcopal notary, with whom, as can be seen by the extant sources, Caroline minuscule began to be used in the see.⁷⁹ It was, however, more likely that the Reform was finally introduced with Bishop Pedro III's successor, Bishop Guido, a monk of French origin and former prior of the cathedral chapter of Lugo.⁸⁰

Meanwhile, in the other main Galician see, Santiago de Compostela, Alfonso VI strengthened relations with Diego Xelmírez, secretary and chancellor of Raymond of Burgundy and a close associate of the Traba family.⁸¹ At that time, Xelmírez was the head of the church of Compostela in charge of administration, and not its bishop, while the see was vacant after Bishop Diego Peláez's forced exile, and remained so due to the succession of unsuitable replacements appointed by Alfonso VI.⁸² Around 1094, the Cluniac monk Dalmacius was chosen as Compostelan bishop by agreement between the king, Pope Urban II, and Abbot Hugh of Cluny. Although he occupied the position for just one year he was not an unfit bishop; Dalmacius achieved for the diocese, recently relocated from Iria to Compostela, the privilege of exemption from the metropolitan jurisdiction of Braga, placing it directly under the authority of Rome. After Dalmacius's death, the king, the Galician count, and the Compostelan chapter looked for a successor of his quality and worthy of the see. In 1100, after years serving the cathedral, Xelmírez was finally named bishop.

Diego Xelmírez shared Alfonso VI's imperial and pro-European ambitions to make the kingdom of Leon-Castile the major Christian realm on the peninsula. It has been already noted that promoting the Way of Saint James and the shrine of Santiago, making of the Galician sanctuary a place of pilgrimage equal to Rome, benefited Alfonso VI's interests.⁸³ But it was not only spiritual prominence that interested both the king and the bishop; trade continued to grow along the Way, ensuring a regular income to the kingdom, thus making the see of Santiago the richest and most renowned bishopric of Leon-Castile.⁸⁴

Once appointed bishop, Xelmírez, like Alfonso VI, seems to have wisely known how to deal with the changing political and religious situation in the early years of the century, carefully managing the see's alliances between a Galician Church resilient to change and a royal house inclined towards unification.⁸⁵ His first goal was to secure the apostolic see, and for that purpose he needed to accept the new rite and introduce it into his diocese, a process that most likely had started with the Cluniac Dalmacius and to which Xelmírez seems to have been most favourably disposed.⁸⁶ Certainly, while in the other Leonese-Castilian territories the reform spread from the monasteries under Cluny, in Galicia the change seems to have arrived through the main sees and their bishops, from where it

⁷⁸ Fletcher, *The Episcopate in the Kingdom of León*, 66 and footnote 156.

⁷⁹ D'Emilio, "The Cathedral Chapter of Lugo," 202.

⁸⁰ García and López, *Episcopologio lucense*, 183-187; Fletcher, *The Episcopate in the Kingdom of León*, 66 and footnote 157.

⁸¹ On Bishop/Archbishop Xelmírez, see Fletcher, *Saint James's Catapult*, chapter 5; B. Reilly, "Santiago and Saint Denis: The French Presence in Eleventh-Century Spain," *The Catholic Historical Review* 54/3 (1968): 467-483; Mosquera Agrelo, "La diócesis de Lugo," 42-53; Rucquoi, "Diego Xelmírez,"

⁸² M. C. Díaz, "La diócesis de Iria-Compostela hasta 1100", in *Historia de las diócesis españolas*, vol. 14. Iglesias de Santiago de Compostela y Tuy-Vigo, coord. J. García Oro (Madrid, 2002), 30-32.

⁸³ See also Díaz, "La diócesis de Iria-Compostela," 39-40; Pallares and Portela, *Historia medieval*, 28-30; Fletcher, *Saint James's Catapult*, chapter 4.

⁸⁴ Abel Vilela, *La ciudad de Lugo*, 64, 67, 81, 105, 371-372, 390-394 on the regulation and protection of trade (*ferias* and markets) along the Way. Fletcher, *The Episcopate in the Kingdom of León*, 53; Mattoso, "Condições económicas e sociais da circulação de códices," 146.

⁸⁵ Fletcher, *Saint James's Catapult*, 114, 163.

⁸⁶ Díaz, "La diócesis de Iria-Compostela," 49.

spread to their dependant diocesan territories.⁸⁷ In 1104 Xelmírez visited the Burgundian abbey, probably in order to learn first-hand the liturgical changes that needed to be implemented as well as to realise the closely related educational improvements that inevitably accompanied the reform.⁸⁸ On his return to Galicia a year later, he started not only to favour the incorporation of French clergy into his cathedral's chapter, which was undergoing profound reform, but also to promote changes within the capitular school, thus welcoming French standards both in liturgy and in script.⁸⁹ The *Historia Compostelana*, the only primary source about Xelmírez's stunning career, highlights the intellectual desolation of the Compostelan cathedral school before the bishop's proactive introduction of the Roman models by naming Geraldus, a native of Beauvais, *magister scholarum* in 1118.⁹⁰ It is widely recognised, however, that the cultural level of the see could not have been as mediocre as suggested, and that this source, the *Compostelana*, is here referring to the canons' poor understanding of the Roman rite, including the script and the language in which it was disseminated until then.⁹¹ On the one hand, Xelmírez himself was taught in Santiago, and was certainly not a man of little culture.⁹² On the other, at the same time as the Old Hispanic rite had long been practised and studied, charters were written and codices were produced, although only fragments of the latter have been preserved, attesting to a good number of skilled scribes.⁹³ Therefore, these scribes, although exposed to Caroline graphic influence from the mid-eleventh century onwards and more than likely also accustomed to reading Caroline minuscule texts since the inception of Xelmírez's new educational program, would have been taught now to correctly employ the new writing system, which they still used in combination with Visigothic in the decades to come. The see being committed to the reform, the bishop had no impediment to continue his and its promotion. At the same time he kept a close bond with Cluny, Xelmírez did not neglect Rome, securing for himself the title of papal legate for all north-western Iberian Peninsula between 1120 and 1124 and, soon after, the transfer of the metropolitan dignity from the church of Mérida to his see.⁹⁴

⁸⁷ The first Galician monastery placed under Cluny's patronage was San Salvador de Villafrío (Lugo), donated in 1075 by a noble, following the example set by the royal family, to ensure his entry to Cluny as a monk. Besides lay donations to the abbey (San Martín de Jubia, granted by the house of Traba in 1113), royal donations continued, although no longer by Alfonso VI but by Urraca (San Vicente de Pombeiro in 1109) and his brother-in-law, Henry of Burgundy, benefactor of Sahagún. Fletcher, *Saint James's Catapult*, 49-50, 239; Rucquoi, "Cluny, el Camino Francés y la Reforma Gregoriana," 119-120.

⁸⁸ Wright, *Late Latin and Early Romance*, 222.

⁸⁹ Fletcher, *Saint James's Catapult*, 163-170 (chapter 7); Mosquera Agrelo, "La diócesis de Lugo," 42-43.

⁹⁰ *Historia Compostelana*, ed. E. Falque Rey (Madrid, 1994), I, 16, 53-54 and II, 1, 240-241. Fletcher, *Saint James's Catapult*, 324-325.

⁹¹ Wright, *Late Latin and Early Romance*, 211.

⁹² Díaz, "La diócesis de Iria-Compostela," 42.

⁹³ On manuscript production (codices) before (*Chronicon Iriense*) and under Xelmírez (*Tumbo A, Historia Compostelana, Codex Calixtinus*) see A. Rucquoi, "De grammaticorum schola: La tradición cultural compostelana en el siglo XII," in *Visitandum est... Santos y cultos en el Codex Calixtinus (Actas del VIIº Congreso Internacional de Estudios Jacobeos)* (Santiago, 2005), 235-254 (3), and Id., "Compostela, centro cultural cosmopolita en los siglos XI y XII," in *El Camino de Santiago: Historia y patrimonio* (Burgos, 2011), 39-55. Fragments of two codices copied in or near the Cathedral of Santiago in transitional Visigothic script have been preserved: Santiago, Catedral, fragm. 3 with a Roman Breviary copied in the late eleventh century (M. C. Díaz y Díaz, *Códices visigóticos de la monarquía leonesa* (León, 1983), 466, nº 201) and Santiago, Catedral, fragm. 1 y 2 with a Roman Missal copied in the early twelfth century (Díaz y Díaz, *Códices*, 465-466, nº 200) – and there must have been many more (see M. Lucas Álvarez, "Paleografía gallega: estado de la cuestión," *Anuario de Estudios Medievales* 21 (1991): 419-470 (429-438 and footnote 29)).

⁹⁴ Fletcher, *Saint James's Catapult*, 211-212.

This complex historical panorama observed in the late eleventh-early twelfth century in the main Galician sees, Lugo and Santiago de Compostela, highlights the different cultural contexts of both centres: on the one hand, there is Lugo, the traditional Galician diocese which had recently lost territory and political and cultural prominence with the restoration of the sees of Braga and Orense, where the new changes arrived slowly under Bishop Amor and, after a turbulent period of political instability, Bishop Pedro III, and on the other hand, there is Santiago, the radiant diocese established as a major point of communication with Europe, the base of the international Way of Saint James, and an ecclesiastical centre equal to Rome.

3.2. Caroline minuscule versus Visigothic script in Galicia

The specific chronology as for the introduction of liturgical reform in Galicia, and the cultural dissimilarity of both sees, schools, and scribes, briefly outlined is perfectly reflected in the graphic characteristics of the extant manuscript sources as well as, more particularly, in the evolution of the script itself.

Previous studies focused on the characteristics of the Visigothic script employed and developed in Galicia have stated, inaccurately as will be noted, that the introduction of Caroline minuscule was achieved more quickly there than in the rest of the Leonese-Castilian territories due to the influence of the Way of Saint James and the cultural prominence of Santiago de Compostela as a major Galician centre.⁹⁵ It has thus consequently been assumed that the graphic influence of foreign models was present in Visigothic script sources from the early twelfth century and that Caroline minuscule was the most common writing system used afterwards, with few examples preserved written in Visigothic script after 1150. The same studies have pointed out, in contrast, that in some rural areas far from the main production centres where the foreign cultural impact was stronger, some remnant Visigothic script examples can be found dating from as late as 1234,⁹⁶ a fact that would make Galicia, besides Toledo, one of the last strongholds of Visigothic script on the Iberian Peninsula. Notwithstanding this latter and correct assertion, however, a close examination of the Galician sources in Visigothic script reveals a much more complex situation.⁹⁷

Thorough compilation and analysis of all extant charters and fragments of codices (no full codex, which can be attributed with certainty to this area, has been preserved) written in Visigothic script and produced in Galician *scriptoria* by scribes trained in Galician schools, indicates that the graphic influence of Caroline minuscule can be dated not to the early twelfth but to the late eleventh century, as attested for most north-western peninsular areas (see table 1). In addition, the first charters written in Caroline date from the second decade of the twelfth century, although the script would not be the main graphic model until many years later. In fact, Visigothic script would remain the main graphic system in use for most of the twelfth century and for almost all Galician scribes. In

⁹⁵ Lucas Álvarez, "Paleografía gallega," 441, 445.

⁹⁶ A. Martínez Salazar, "Diplomática gallega. ¿El último representante de la escritura visigoda?," *Boletín de la Real Academia Gallega* 8 (1913): 49-56. Charter written at the monastery of Almerezo (Visigothic minuscule with strong Caroline influence), now lost.

⁹⁷ A collection of edited charters written in Visigothic script in Galicia has been published in A. Castro Correa, *Colección diplomática altomedieval de Galicia I: documentación editada en escritura visigótica (662-1234)* (A Coruña, 2011). Some of the unedited charters, written or copied in the diocese of Lugo, have been studied in A. Castro Correa, "La escritura visigótica en Galicia. I. Diócesis lucense" (PhD diss., Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 2012), and will be published shortly. See also A. Castro Correa, "La escritura visigótica en Galicia. Diócesis lucense y mindoniense: Cuestiones metodológicas y estado de la investigación," in *Estudiar el pasado: aspectos metodológicos de la investigación en Ciencias de la Antigüedad y de la Edad Media. Proceedings of the First Postgraduate Conference on Studies of Antiquity and Middle Ages (Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona, 26-28th October 2010)*, ed. A. Castro Correa et al. (Oxford, 2012), 370-375.

comparison with other Leonese-Castilian areas, therefore, although the graphic influence can be confirmed as received in the same period, the process of transition from Visigothic script to Caroline minuscule was slower in Galicia than in any other part of the Iberian Peninsula. Indeed, the extant sources show that in the north-western peninsula it took more than a hundred years for Galician men of letters to abandon the script they had been using since at least the late ninth century in favour of the new foreign one (see table 2). This peculiarity makes the corpus of Galician sources the ideal basis for studying the process of graphic transition, since both scripts, Visigothic and Caroline, were in use simultaneously and influenced each other for generations.

<i>area</i>	<i>first Caroline minuscule influence</i>	<i>first charter in Caroline</i>	<i>transition completed (last charter in Visigothic script)</i>	<i>from the first charter in Caroline minuscule to the last in Visigothic script</i>
Leon-Castile	mid-11 th c.	1110s-1120s	1120s	c. 10 years
Cantabria	late-11 th c.	1120s	1136	c. 15 years
Asturias	late-11 th c.	1116	1166	c. 50 years
Portugal	mid-11 th c.	1110s	1172	c. 60 years
Galicia	late-11 th c.	1110	1199 (1234)	c. 90 years

TABLE 1. Chronology of the graphic transition in northern Iberia given the extant sources.⁹⁸

<i>production centre</i>		<i>first charter in transitional Visigothic script</i>	<i>first charter in Caroline minuscule script</i>	<i>last charter in transitional Visigothic script</i>	<i>coexistence (years)</i>	<i>total years for the change</i>
Lugo	diocese	1091	1113	1196	83	105
	see	1091	1113	1156	43	64
Santiago	diocese	1050	1110	1199 (1234)	89 (124)	149 (184)
	see	[1050]	1110	1194	84	[144]

TABLE 2. Chronology of the graphic transition in Lugo and Santiago.⁹⁹

⁹⁸ For full references to these sources see Castro Correa, “Visigothic script versus Caroline minuscule” (LMS diss., Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies, 2015).

⁹⁹ Id. and A. Castro Correa, “La escritura visigótica en Galicia. I. Diócesis lucense”.

TABLE 3. Types of Visigothic script and their chronological distribution from the mid-eleventh century to 1200. Lugo diocese.

TABLE 4. Types of Visigothic script and their chronological distribution from the mid-eleventh century to 1200. Santiago de Compostela diocese.

A closer look at the chronology and typological variant of the Galician sources in Visigothic script and their distribution according to their most likely production centres (see table 2, 3 and 4), provides yet more remarkable data. In contrast to what might be expected given the cultural importance of Santiago de Compostela and the constant flow of foreign visitors and codices it received, it was in that centre, see and diocese, that the transition from Visigothic to Caroline was slower. Moreover, it shows, as a consequence, a very peculiar graphical acculturation represented in a transitional variant

mix of cursive Visigothic script and Caroline minuscule.¹⁰⁰ The interaction between Visigothic script and Caroline minuscule in Galicia differed, therefore, from all the other northern realms in chronology and style. There were even differences between the main sees and their dependent territories, an observation that reflects the particular local cultural context during the eleventh and the twelfth centuries already discussed.

Although the full corpus of sources in Visigothic script from the see and the diocese of Lugo is abundant, showing the work of many accomplished scribes from whom, unfortunately, only charters have survived and no codex,¹⁰¹ there are ten extant original charters from which to study the graphic influence of Caroline minuscule in the see (see table 5).¹⁰² Their chronology ranges from 1091 to 1156 with the following distribution: two charters from the late eleventh century, five from the first half of the twelfth, and three from the second half. The oldest extant charter in Caroline minuscule in the see dates from 1113.¹⁰³ Thus five of those ten Visigothic script charters and their amanuenses are contemporary to the new script. Besides, cursive and minuscule Visigothic still continued to be used in the see and in the diocese, the former typological variant until 1128 and the latter until 1107.

The ten extant sources useful for the purpose of this study, all written in the minuscule typological variant of Visigothic, record transactions to which the cathedral was the main beneficiary and can be attributed with some certainty to the work of six scribes who, judging by the codicographic and palaeographic characteristics of the charters they wrote, received specific graphical training to develop their task as scribes in the Lucense cathedral school.¹⁰⁴

The first charter used here to analyse the graphic introduction of Caroline minuscule elements into the Visigothic script in Lugo's cathedral scriptorium was written in 1091 by Menendo.¹⁰⁵ Although the charter, which represents Countess Aldonza's will to the Cathedral of Lugo including a *uilla* in Chamoso, is unsigned, its highly calligraphic characteristics make it possible to identify its hand as that of Menendo. He was also the author of two other original charters, an acknowledgment by Queen Urraca of Lugo's properties in Retorta dated 1123 with a very elegant first line in Visigothic capitals

¹⁰⁰ On the stages of Visigothic script, see A. Castro Correa, "Looking to the past with an eye in the future: dating and placing Visigothic script" (under review).

¹⁰¹ A full list of charters and fragments of codices is provided in Castro Correa, "La escritura visigótica en Galicia," also with some notes about what must have been the cathedral's library.

¹⁰² On Galician schools and production centres, see Castro Correa, "La escritura visigótica en Galicia," 2-45. Copies, like Madrid, Archivo Histórico Nacional, Clero, carp. 1325A, n^o 3 in transitional minuscule most likely written in Lugo's see, are not considered in this study. Also, charter Madrid, Archivo Histórico Nacional, Clero, carp. 1325C, n^o 7. May 19, 1119 (Castro Correa, "La escritura visigótica en Galicia," 360-364) was written by the personal notary of the Leonese count Suarío Bermúdez (M. Recuero Astray, *Alfonso VII (1126-1157)* (Burgos, 2003), 74 et seqq.) and, thus, although it could be, cannot be supposed an example of the script taught in Lugo's see. There are 35 charters preserved for the whole diocese: Madrid, Archivo Histórico Nacional, Clero, carp. 1082, n^o 16; carp. 1126, n^o 4, 5, 7; carp. 1197, n^o 1; carp. 1214, n^o 6; carp. 1239, n^o 19; carp. 1240, n^o 3, 4, 6, 7, 8; carp. 1325A, n^o 2, 3; carp. 1325B, n^o 18, 19, 25; carp. 1325C, n^o 1, 2, 9, 11, 13, 21; carp. 1325D, n^o 1, 13; carp. 1325F, n^o 8; carp. 1325H, n^o 19; Lugo, Archivo de la Catedral, perg. 1, 34, 44, 46, 47, 48, Libro X de privilegios, leg. 2, n^o 2; Schøyen Collection, mss. 590/51. On their detailed graphic characteristics, see Castro Correa, "La escritura visigótica en Galicia," 814-827, 850-859.

¹⁰³ Madrid, Archivo Histórico Nacional, Clero, carp. 1325C, n^o 4.

¹⁰⁴ On the categorisation of the training of early medieval scribes based on analysis of their script see, among others, A. Petrucci, "Literacy and graphic culture of early medieval scribes," in *Writers and Readers in Medieval Italy. Studies in the History of Written Culture* (Yale, 1995), 77-102.

¹⁰⁵ Madrid, Archivo Histórico Nacional, Clero, carp. 1325B, n^o 18. February 27, 1091. Castro Correa, "La escritura visigótica en Galicia," 330-337.

[PLATE 1],¹⁰⁶ and a sale of a land near Lugo dated 1124,¹⁰⁷ as well as a copy of a royal diploma,¹⁰⁸ which he did sign. Menendo shows himself to be a skilled scribe with excellent graphic abilities and aesthetic sensibility who took care in the elaboration of his charters, three of which are ruled in dry point with large margins and embellished initials. Although no examples have been preserved, in all likelihood, he also copied codices. Trained in minuscule Visigothic, he was not unfamiliar with cursive features (see table 5), such as the simplified form for *qui*, although they are not often seen in his hand. Already in his first manuscript, which must correspond to his early career, Menendo's script shows subtle influence from the continental abbreviation system through a moderate use of shortenings by suprascript letters for the syllables *pri* and *pro*, continental forms of the syllables *per* and *pre* – with a horizontal stroke crossing the descender of *p* in the first case and a line above *p* for the latter – and use of a sign similar to a semicircle for the ending *-us*, employed just once. In Menendo's second and third charters, the evolution of his hand is noticeable with a clear increase of Caroline minuscule influence; to the previous continental forms he added the abbreviation of the possessive *noster* with theme in *r*, suspension by a short horizontal line drawn through the ascender of the letter *b* in the personal pronouns *nobis* and *uobis*, the ending *-ur* after *t* and *-unt* after *r*, a more elaborate use of suprascript letters now also for *modo*, *uero*, and *mihi*, contraction of *quod* as *qd*, and *con* and *est* by a short horizontal line surmounted to *c* and *e*. This foreign graphic influence is even stronger in the copy he made of the royal diploma, which features suspension for the ending *-ur* after *m* and some *notae iuris*.

Between the first and second charters written by Menendo, three other equally skilled scribes worked for the Cathedral of Lugo, the first one of them Archdeacon Juan. In 1092,¹⁰⁹ he documented the will *pro remedio animae* ordered by Count Froilán Bermúdez of the house of Traba, to the Cathedral of St. Mary of Lugo, in which he gives one of his *uillae* near the river Chamoso. Some of Froilán's children signed the document as witnesses, among them Gonzalo, *presul* and bishop of the nearby see of Mondoñedo (1071-1112), Pedro (with autograph signature), Rodrigo, Elvira, and Munia Fróilaz. Also witnesses of the transaction were archdeacons Rodrigo and Juan (autograph sign), Bishop Amor of Lugo and Judge Sandino Petriz (autograph sign). Juan's interpretation of the Visigothic graphic model in this charter presents an early but intense influence of the Caroline minuscule abbreviation system, attested by the continental forms of *episcopus*, *nomen*, and *quod*, use of Caroline suspension for the syllables *per* and *pre*, and *-er-* after *t*, suspension by suprascript letter for *pra/pri/pro* and use of the Tironian system for the conjunction *et* and the syllable *con* in the signature box.

Several years after Juan, in 1106, Vermudo wrote another charter, also in minuscule Visigothic with Caroline features, recording the will of Pedro García and his wife Elvira to Bishop Pedro II of Lugo.¹¹⁰ His hand shows the same quality and similar external influence in the abbreviation system as his colleagues before.

A year later, in 1107, *presbiter* Vimara continued using the same typological variant, now showing more fluency in the incorporation of exogenous elements. He writes in a less calligraphic hand, despite the fact that the charter is recording a direct donation to the see witnessed by Bishop Pedro,

¹⁰⁶ Madrid, Archivo Histórico Nacional, Clero, carp. 1325C, nº 11. March 8, 1123.

¹⁰⁷ Madrid, Archivo Histórico Nacional, Clero, carp. 1325C, nº 13. May 12, 1124.

¹⁰⁸ Lugo, Archivo de la Catedral, Libro X de pergaminos, leg. 2, nº 2. June 30, 987: Alfonso III (866-910) confirms the limits of the *señorío* of the see as identified by previous monarchs and grants to Lugo money, a dowry, and new territories.

¹⁰⁹ Madrid, Archivo Histórico Nacional, Clero, carp. 1325B, nº 19. March 3, 1092. Castro Correa, "La escritura visigótica en Galicia," 338-342.

¹¹⁰ Madrid, Archivo Histórico Nacional, Clero, carp. 1325C, nº 1. February 1, 1106. Castro Correa, "La escritura visigótica en Galicia," 347-350.

Archdeacon Pelayo and Judge Pelayo, who include their personal signatures.¹¹¹ Vimara frequently uses suspensions by suprascript letter, not only for the syllables *pro*, *pri*, and *qui*, but also for *uero*, *hoc*, *modo*, and *tibi*, the Tironian *notae* for *con* and *est*, and the continental forms for the contraction of the syllables *per* and *per* and for *episcopus*, *presbiter*, and *quod*, besides the suspension of *-(t)er*, *-(t, m)ur*, *-(r)unt*, and *-(m)en-*. There is still no evidence of external graphic influence in the alphabet, apart from the continuous use of uncial *a* as numeral exponent.

The next scribe, Pedro, is already coeval to the first scribe using the new script in the see since his charter dates to 1130.¹¹² As a consequence, his handwriting is a neat example of how the new writing system was becoming increasingly dominant: a Visigothic minuscule with Caroline minuscule *ductus* full of Caroline minuscule abbreviations. He wrote the will of Count Gutierre Vermúdez and Countess Toda to the Cathedral of Lugo, which includes part of the Monastery of Salvador de Chamoso, very close to the see. Pedro's hand is highly calligraphic, his initials bearing careful flourishes. The disposition of the text within the parchment, ruled in dry point, is careful and elegant. He included all the Caroline minuscule contractions already mentioned, with the exception of the ending *-(r)unt*, besides adding some hitherto unseen ones in Galician Visigothic examples, such as the suprascript letter for the syllable *cri*. Also, he was the first scribe to use diacritic *i* at the end of a word and when two *i*'s came together.

The last three examples to be considered here (see table 5) date to the second half of the twelfth century and belong to the same scribe, Rodrigo [PLATE 2].¹¹³ All three record sales around Lugo of lay people whose relationship with the see is unknown and who apparently turned to the cathedral scribes to elaborate their charters. Regardless of the social status of the grantors and beneficiaries involved, Rodrigo's hand is still calligraphic and elegant, especially in his last charter, where his advanced age can also be glimpsed by the strokes of the letters. Rodrigo's hand shows Caroline minuscule *ductus*, not Caroline letters, and Caroline minuscule abbreviations as usual. His hand can easily be compared with that of Menendo as a late example of this transitional period in Lugo: the exogenous abbreviations used by Rodrigo are ending *-us* marked by a semicircle, continental *per* and *pre*, endings *-(t)er*, *-(t)ur*, *-(r)unt*, suprascript letter for *cri*, *mihi*, *modo*, *pra/pri/pro*, *qua/qui/quo*, *sanctus* and *uero*, Caroline minuscule forms for *autem*, *nomen*, *quod*, *tempus*, *uobis*, *post*, and *notae iuris* for *est*.

After 1156 a minuscule Visigothic script with strong Caroline minuscule influence continued to be used in the diocese, though not in the see, its last example dated 1196.¹¹⁴

The study of how Visigothic script evolved throughout the centuries in the see and diocese of Santiago de Compostela is rendered more difficult by two considerable limitations: the quantity of the preserved sources and their state of preservation. When, in 1129, the cathedral of Santiago started the cartularisation project that resulted in the Tumbo A, which was intended to facilitate consultation of the vast corpus of documents the see must have possessed at that time¹¹⁵ by copying them together and in the new, more legible, script, all the Visigothic script charters that had been

¹¹¹ Madrid, Archivo Histórico Nacional, Clero, carp. 1325C, nº 2. May 16, 1107. Castro Correa, "La escritura visigótica en Galicia," 351-357.

¹¹² Madrid, Archivo Histórico Nacional, Clero, carp. 1325C, nº 21. October 30, 1130. Castro Correa, "La escritura visigótica en Galicia," 370-374.

¹¹³ Lugo, Archivo de la Catedral, perg. 34. September 17, [1152]; Madrid, Archivo Histórico Nacional, Clero, carp. 1325D, nº 13. December 28, 1155; Lugo, Archivo de la Catedral, perg. 48. April 16, 1156. Castro Correa, "La escritura visigótica en Galicia," 379-383.

¹¹⁴ Madrid, Archivo Histórico Nacional, Clero (San Vicente del Pino), carp. 1197, nº 1. Castro Correa, "La escritura visigótica en Galicia," 393-395.

¹¹⁵ López Alsina estimates that there were more than a thousand charters in total (F. López Alsina, *La ciudad de Santiago de Compostela en la alta edad media* (Santiago de Compostela, 2015), 42-43).

produced in the previous years were dismissed. Some of these documents were lost forever since only the most relevant ones, concerning property of the see, were copied. Fortunately, however, and in contrast with Lugo's context, besides the cathedral centre there were many highly relevant monastic institutions nearby, such as San Martín Pinario or San Payo de Antealtares, which did not decide to reorganise their charters into a codex in the early twelfth century, thus retaining a considerable abundant Visigothic script corpus.¹¹⁶ The state of preservation of these extant charters is, however, generally poor if not very poor.¹¹⁷ Consequently, it is not possible to establish with certainty how the graphic evolution in the Compostelan see proceeded in the same detail as in Lugo, although the extant Visigothic script charters enable at least a partial approach that, though incomplete, reveals an especially rich, diverse, and distinctive graphic context in late-eleventh and early twelfth-century Santiago.

The influence of the new written system is attested in the minuscule variant of Visigothic script in the diocese of Santiago from at least the 1060s, although the oldest charter that can be considered with some certainty to be the product of a scribe trained in the cathedral school dates from 1095 (see table 6).¹¹⁸ There are a few charters in minuscule Visigothic script with Caroline minuscule features that record texts dated earlier, but their poor state of preservation makes it impossible to determine whether they are originals or copies and to provide information about their material authors.¹¹⁹ The 1095 charter was written by Deacon Ordoño Eusebiz and records the foundation act of the Monastery of San Julián de Moraime by Countess Argilo. All the eminent local ecclesiastical personalities of that time act as witnesses of this document, adding their signatures at the bottom of the parchment. They are the bishops of the sees of Santiago, Lugo, Mondoñedo, Tuy, and Orense; the abbots of the monasteries of Moraime, Antealtares, and Pinario; and judges Pedro Danieliz, Sarracino Gundisalviz, and Pelayo Gudestéiz. Ordoño's hand is highly calligraphic, extremely elegant, and so neat that it can be assumed not only that he was trained at the cathedral school but also that he was one of its best scribes, undoubtedly used not only to write charters but to copy codices, though none are extant. As for the continental features absorbed (see table 6), it must be said that Ordoño stayed loyal to the model, not using any exogenous letters and only very few abbreviations, like *per/pre*, some examples of suprascript letter for *qui*, the Tironian sign for *est*, and a few others (contraction of *propter*, *episcopus*, *quotum*, and *quod*).

A not so carefully written charter was penned by García Martinz a few years later.¹²⁰ It presents a completely different graphic reception of Caroline minuscule traits since it frequently includes closed

¹¹⁶ On the medieval, pre-1200, sources preserved for the cathedral and major monasteries of Santiago de Compostela, see López Alsina, *La ciudad de Santiago*, 27-31.

Charters in Visigothic in transition to Caroline minuscule written in the diocese of Santiago de Compostela: Santiago de Compostela, Archivo Histórico Diocesano (Pinario), San Martín, carp. 79, nº 11, 14, 15, 27, 28, 29, 31, carp. 80, nº 10; Santiago de Compostela, Archivo Histórico Universitario de Santiago, Moraime, nº 2, Pinario, nº 18, 30, 33, 42, 44, 45, 47, 48, 49, 53, Colección Blanco Cicerón, nº 4, 15, 137, 138, 186, 188, 198; La Coruña, Archivo del Reino de Galicia, nº 2, 261, 262, 272, 282, 496, 497, 499, 1183, Colección Vaamonde Lores, carp. 5, nº 1/5; Madrid, Archivo Histórico Nacional, Clero (San Martín Pinario), carp. 512, nº 9.

¹¹⁷ On the causes, see A. Castro Correa, "The reconstruction of early medieval Spanish manuscript sources," *Early Medieval Europe* 22/1 (2014): 69-87.

¹¹⁸ Santiago de Compostela, Archivo Histórico Universitario de Santiago, Moraime, nº 2. June 18, 1095. Edited by M. Lucas Álvarez, "El monasterio de San Julián de Moraime en Galicia (Notas documentales)," in *Homenaje a Don Agustín Millares Carlo*, vol. II (Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, 1975), 605-643, nº 2.

¹¹⁹ For example, Santiago de Compostela, Archivo Histórico Diocesano (Pinario), San Martín, 79.14, with the sign similar to a semicircle to mark the ending *-us* and continental abbreviation *h(er)*, dated 1070.

¹²⁰ Santiago de Compostela, Archivo Histórico Universitario de Santiago, Pinario, nº 33. February 17, 1110. Edited by M. Lucas Álvarez, *El archivo del monasterio de San Martiño de Fóra o Pinario de Santiago de Compostela* (Sada, 1999), nº 40.

a throughout the text as well as the sign similar to a semicircle for the ending *-us*, the suspension of *(m)en-* by a *titulus* above *m*, the Tironian sign for *et*, and the continental form of the personal pronouns *nobis/uobis*, none of which are attested earlier in the Compostelan examples.

Caroline minuscule influence continued to grow, as indicated by the next relevant charter, dated 1122.¹²¹ Its author, Gundesindo, does not show the same graphic skills as Ordoño, the lack of horizontality in the text layout on the parchment being especially striking. His hand is, however, calligraphic. As for new continental features, Gundesindo regularly uses a semicircle for the ending *-us*, which has been seen before though not as frequently as here, and the suspension of *-er-* and *-ur* on *t* besides many more examples of suprascript letters, for *pro/pri*, *qui*, *uero*, *tibi*, and *nihil*, Tironian *notae* for *et* and *con*, *notae iuris* for *sunt*, and other Caroline minuscule abbreviations (*hoc*, *sicut*, *quod*, *nobis*, and *nomen*).

In order to find the first charter produced in minuscule Visigothic script, not only with evidence of Caroline minuscule abbreviations (semicircle for the ending *-us*, continental *per*, suspension of *-t(er)* and *-t(ur)*, Tironian *et*, *notae iuris* for *est*, and Caroline forms of *uester*, *uobis/nobis*, *tempore*, and *episcopus*) but also *ductus*, we must wait until 1163, when the scribe Pedro recorded a sale between Vermudo Fróilaz and the church of San Jorge de Torres [PLATE 3].¹²²

So far, the transitional Visigothic script developed in Santiago seems to be as expected, a minuscule Visigothic script with exogenous features. It was contemporary to cursive (until 1133), semi-cursive (1139), and minuscule (1188) Visigothic script in that diocese, as well as to Caroline minuscule since at least the second decade of the twelfth century (first charter preserved dating 1110¹²³). However, the mutual influence of the two scripts, traditional and European, appears to have been far more chaotic in the Compostelan see as a result of its cultural milieu, since in the first half of the twelfth century, and therefore coeval to the first manuscripts written in Caroline, the predominant graphic variant was cursive Visigothic script, both pure and hybrid.

Among the extant sources produced in the diocese of Santiago de Compostela that allow a thorough palaeographic analysis, thus omitting those in a state of preservation so poor that it prevents a full understanding of the scribes' graphic features, there are twenty charters written by amanuenses most likely trained in the cathedral school which are relevant for understanding how the graphic transition developed. Their chronology ranges from 1050 to 1150 for the see and to 1167 for the diocese, and mostly concentrated in the first half of the twelfth century.

Petrus Danieliz's charter dated to 1115 is one of the first and most significant ones (see table 7) given the prominence of the witnesses who signed the document.¹²⁴ The signatures of these people are not autograph, though perhaps some of the signs drawn with them are, but even so they are significant for the script in which they were written. In 1115, when the Roman rite must have been at least already introduced in Galicia, if not fully established, and Caroline minuscule was already known and practised, not only Bishop Xelmírez but also the Archbishop of Toledo and papal legate Bernard and

¹²¹ Santiago de Compostela, Archivo Histórico Universitario de Santiago, Blanco Cicerón, nº 188. September 9, 1122. Edited by M. Lucas Álvarez, "Colligere fragmenta: documentos en escritura visigótica del Archivo Histórico Universitario de Santiago de Compostela," *Historia. Instituciones. Documentos* 19 (1992): 267-276, nº 5.

¹²² La Coruña, Archivo del Reino de Galicia, perg. 499. May 6, 1163.

¹²³ AHUS, Pergaminos Blanco Cicerón, núm. 11.

¹²⁴ La Coruña, Archivo del Reino de Galicia, Vaamonde Lores, nº 1183. May 15, 1115. Bishop Xelmírez recognises the independence of the Monastery of San Martín Pinario. Another extant charter, Madrid, Archivo Histórico Nacional, Clero (Pinario), carp. 512, nº 9 (dated 1122), bears Xelmírez's signature, again in cursive Visigothic script (Wright, *Late Latin and Early Romance*, 235; Fletcher, *The Episcopate in the Kingdom of León*, 116). As example of this transitional variant from cursive Visigothic to Caroline minuscule, see PLATE 4.

the Cluniac Bishop of Braga Mauricio among others, did not seem to have had any problem in letting the scribe write in cursive Visigothic script, adding their signatures in cursive *elongata*. Besides these signatures and the content of the document, Danieliz's hand is also significant: *c* and *e* preserving the characteristic cursive stroke to the left side, *c* with its first stroke in a spiral, a sign similar to a G-clef for the ending *-us*, Visigothic *per* and *qui* combined with diacritic *i*, a semicircle for the ending *-us*, continental *pre*, suspension of *-(t)er-*, *-(t)ur*, and *-(m)en-*, suprascript letter for *pri*, *qua/qui/quo*, *tibi*, *modo*, and *uir*, Tironian sign for *con*, and continental forms of the abbreviations of *tempore*, *episcopus*, *quod*, *secundus*, *uobis*, and *noster*. Danieliz thus presents a perfect cursive Visigothic script, according to the model, that nevertheless has strong Caroline minuscule influence. This graphical contamination, though already solid in the first examples of transitional cursive Visigothic, would continue to develop during the next decades. Thus, one of the last examples of this typological transitional variant, dated to 1150¹²⁵ and written by the cardinal Pelagius (see table 7), displays a very calligraphic cursive Visigothic script, with G-clef and semicircle for *-us*, Visigothic *per* but Caroline minuscule *pre*, Visigothic *qui* and also suprascript *qui*, and Caroline minuscule forms for *-(t)er*, *-(t)ur*, *-(r)unt*, and *-(m)en-*.

The fact that when Caroline minuscule began to be known in the Iberian Peninsula through, mostly, the abundance of trans-Pyrenean codices, its graphic characteristics started to mix with those of the minuscule typological variant of Visigothic script, as happened in all northern production centres, results reasonable bearing in mind the external graphic similarities of the two scripts; both minuscule types. The scribes who were first exposed to Caroline minuscule in the Leonese-Castilian kingdom were those used to read and write codices in minuscule Visigothic script. It is logical to imagine that in time the incorporation of Caroline minuscule features within their texts must have been unavoidable. The same scribes who wrote codices were also commissioned to write charters. Therefore, those highly skilled scribes, taught to write in minuscule Visigothic, must have been responsible for the first charters in transitional minuscule Visigothic. That in the see of Santiago, however, the graphic influence is seen first and most intensively in the sources preserved in cursive Visigothic script is by all accounts a remarkable development. The extant sources do not show such a cursive variant in transition to Caroline minuscule in Lugo, either in the see or in the diocese as a whole. This transitional cursive results an extremely rare graphic acculturation also in the rest of the Leonese-Castilian kingdom; as example, there is only one charter in the Cathedral of Leon dating from 1118.¹²⁶ The exception to this trend is the *scriptorium* of the monastery of Sahagún.¹²⁷ Analysis of the corpus of charters in Visigothic script from Sahagún¹²⁸ reveals Caroline minuscule influence in both minuscule – the predominant typology in use until 1131 – and in cursive hands – with its last example dated 1109 – starting in the same decade, 1060s. However, the typological variant that presents the strongest influence of Caroline minuscule in its alphabet and abbreviation system, with its first charter dated to 1104 at Sahagún, is the minuscule and not the cursive, thus contrasting with what can be seen in Santiago's manuscript sources.

There are two main explanations for the graphic peculiarity of the transitional Visigothic scripts in Santiago. First, common to the Compostelan see and Sahagún, is the direct Cluniac influence. Second, exclusive to Galician Visigothic script, is the long life cycle of the cursive typological variant given that

¹²⁵ La Coruña, Archivo del Reino de Galicia, perg. 497: March 7, 1150. Sale of Nuño Peláez's *hereditates* to Countess Lupa in San Cristóbal de Dorneá.

¹²⁶ León, Archivo de la Catedral, nº 317. Ruiz Asencio, "Cronología de la desaparición," 104, fig. 7.

¹²⁷ See M. Herrero de la Fuente, "De Cluny a Sahagún: La escritura carolina en el monasterio de Sahagún (siglos XI-XII)," in *Le statut du scripteur au Moyen Age : Actes du XIIe colloque scientifique du Comité international de paléographie latine (Cluny, 17-20 juillet 1998)*, ed. M.-C. Hubert, E. Poulle, and M. H. Smith (Paris, 2000), 29-40 (33-35). B. Shailor, "The Scriptorium of San Sahagún: A Period of Transition," in *Santiago, Saint-Denis, and Saint Peter: the Reception of the Roman Liturgy in Leon-Castile in 1080*, ed. B. F. Reilly (New York, 1985), 41-61.

¹²⁸ M. Herrero de la Fuente, *Colección diplomática del monasterio de Sahagún*, vol. 2, 3 (León, 1988).

pure minuscule Visigothic script is rare in Galicia unlike in the other Leonese-Castilian centres.¹²⁹ The former explains the intense external graphic influence, also favoured by Santiago's status not only as the main Galician centre of culture but also as a highly significant European one. The latter explains why this influence was received also, and more intensively, in the cursive variant, since this was the predominant script when Caroline minuscule started to be used by the master scribes of the Compostelan see.

4. Epilogue

This study discusses how the massive arrival of books with the new rite copied in Caroline minuscule, the cultural pressure from Europe, and the political interests of kings and ecclesiastical personalities opened the path for the replacement of the old rite with the Roman liturgy and for the change of Visigothic script to Caroline minuscule throughout the Iberian Christian kingdoms. Once the new rite was finally accepted, the affluence of Roman texts increased as did the production of codices with the Roman rite in Iberia, although in the first decades some exemplars were still copied in the traditional Visigothic script system. The chaotic graphic situation and the educational differences it highlighted, since the sources attest that clerics were not only ignorant of the new writing system but also could not read, understand, and pronounce the Latin, led to changes far beyond the liturgy resulting in scholastic reorganisation and further development of written production. Scribes needed to learn the new standard, following the requests of their patrons and superiors, and while at first graphic change was only required for liturgical texts, it soon after was applied to all written production, charters included. From the ninth-century onwards in the north-east Iberian Peninsula and from the mid- late-eleventh century onwards in the Leonese-Castilian kingdom, Visigothic script scribes attested to the cultural pressure of the imported new written system by developing very distinctive transitional typological variants. However, just as the Hispanic rite was preserved, Visigothic script continued to be used. In the production of charters it was used for some hundred years longer, especially in the main production centres that chose to do so either as a cultural statement or just for practicality. The change from Visigothic to Caroline minuscule was not an unconscious process ensued from the logical graphic evolution that progressively transforms a script into a new distinctive one, but the result of a conscious substitution of one graphic system for another that happened to be more legible and consistent with the cultural and political unification of the Iberian Peninsula and its relationship with Europe.¹³⁰ The study of how the scribes of each production centre achieved this graphic transition unveils the role that each ecclesiastical institution had as well as their political and cultural context.

At least from the 1050s onwards in the Santiago's diocese and the 1090s in Lugo's, the extant sources suggest that amanuenses tried to adapt to the graphic change, thus developing the Visigothic transitional variants.¹³¹ They were already leaving behind their previous generation of scribes who,

¹²⁹ This variant has been supposed to have been introduced into charters in Castile first, then in Leon, with the change of dynasty (Vermudo III of Leon to Fernando I of Navarre in 1037), since it was the main typological variant in use in Navarre. See A. Millares Carlo, *Consideraciones sobre la escritura visigótica cursiva* (León, 1973), 73; M. Herrero de la Fuente and J. A. Fernández Flórez, "Sobre la escritura visigótica en León y Castilla durante su etapa primitiva (ss. VII-X): algunas reflexiones," in *La escritura visigótica en la Península Ibérica: nuevas aportaciones* (Barcelona, 2012), 55-104 (91); A. Castro Correa, "La escritura visigótica redonda en Galicia: documentos de la Catedral de Lugo," in *La escritura visigótica en la Península Ibérica: nuevas aportaciones*, ed. J. Alturo, A. Castro and M. Torras (Barcelona, 2012), 105-114.

¹³⁰ On this concept see Mundó and Alturo, "Problemàtica de les scriptures del períodes de transició".

¹³¹ For discussion on to what extent were the scribes aware of the graphic differences between writing systems, polygraphism in twelfth-century Galicia, teaching practices and the social status of Visigothic and Caroline minuscule script scribes in this context, see A. Castro Correa, "The regional study of Visigothic script: Visigothic

because of their age, were unable to adjust. In most of the northern peninsular areas, including the Catalan northeast, it seems that it took only one generation to replace the traditional script with the new one. In Galicia, however, the process was much slower, particularly in Santiago, where, after nearly half a century of transitional Visigothic we find the first example written in Caroline. Visigothic script continued to be used for writing charters for almost a hundred years after that. The manuscript sources from Galicia suggest that, while a generation of scribes began to change their script, some of their colleagues and not only those of advanced age, continued to prefer Visigothic. This Visigothic persistence is due to the specific historical context in Galicia. Sources seem to suggest that, while in Santiago scribes lived in a prominent cultural centre, capable by itself of determining the rhythm of graphic change, Lucense scribes could not help but change at the pace imposed. But independently of how we prefer to interpret how this period of graphic transition was, the fact is that it was not at all uncommon to find Visigothic script scribes in mid-twelfth century Galicia together with Caroline minuscule ones.

script vs. Caroline minuscule in Galicia," in *'Change' in medieval and Renaissance scripts and manuscripts: proceedings of the 19th Colloquium of the Comité international de paléographie latine* (Berlin, September 16-18, 2015) (in press).

year	shelfmark & scribe	uncial <i>a</i> (exp.)	<i>t+j</i>	<i>I-longa</i>	<i>i</i>	square <i>r</i> after <i>o</i>																
1091-1124	1325B18 1325C11 1325C13 Menendo	Y	Y	Y	N	Y*	<i>b, i, l, m/n, p, t</i>	<i>i</i>	N	<i>r, t</i>	<i>b, n, t</i>	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	<i>m, t</i>	Y	Y	
1092	1325B19 Juan archid.	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	<i>b, j, m/n</i>	N	N	<i>r, n, t</i>	<i>b, n</i>	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N	
1106	1325C1 Vermudo	N	Y	Y*	N	Y*	<i>b, l, m, n, t</i>	<i>t</i>	N	<i>r</i>	<i>t</i>	Y	N	N	Y	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	
1107	1325C2 Vimara presbiter	Y	N (<i>ci</i>)	Y*	N	Y	<i>b, d, j, m, c</i>	N	N	<i>r</i>	<i>b, n, t</i>	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	<i>m, t</i>	Y	Y	
1130	1325C21 Pedro	Y	Y	Y*	Y	Y	<i>b, i, m, n, r, t</i>	<i>i, l, b</i>	N	<i>r, t</i>	<i>b, n, t</i>	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	<i>m, t</i>	N	Y	
1152-1156	ACLu34 1325D13 ACLu48 Rodrigo	N	N (<i>ci</i>)/ Y	Y*	Y	Y*	<i>b, i, m, n</i>	<i>b, c, d</i>	N	<i>r</i>	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y*	Y	Y	Y	N	

TABLE 5. Scribes writing in minuscule Visigothic script with Caroline minuscule influence in Lugo (see).

year	shelfmark & scribe	uncial α (exp.)	<i>tsj</i>	<i>l-longa</i>	<i>i</i>	square <i>r</i> after <i>o</i>																		
1095	AHUSMo2 Ordoño Euseviz diac.	N	Y	Y	N	Y	<i>b, l, m/n, t</i>	N	N	<i>r, t</i>	<i>b</i>	Y	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
1110	AHUSPin 33 García Martinz	N	Y	Y*	N	Y*	<i>m</i>	<i>m</i>	N	<i>r</i>	<i>b, n</i>	N	N	N	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N	Y	
1122	AHUSBC 188 Gundesinde	Y	N (<i>ci</i>)	Y	N	Y	<i>d, m/n</i>	<i>i, t</i>	N	<i>t</i>	<i>b, m/n</i>	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N
1126	AHUSBC 138	N	Y	N	N	Y	<i>b</i>	<i>n</i>	N	<i>r, t</i>	Y	Y	N	N	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y
1135	AHUSBC 137/4 Galindo	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	N	<i>i</i>	N	<i>r</i>	N	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N
1153	AHUSPin 49 Arias Pelagici presbiter	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	<i>b, i, n, t</i>	N	<i>r</i>	N	Y	N	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N
1163	ARG499 Pedro	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	<i>b, d, t</i>	<i>c, d, j/i, n, t</i>	N	N	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	N	N

TABLE 6. Scribes writing in minuscule Visigothic script with Caroline minuscule influence in Santiago (see).

year	shelfmark & scribe	uncial <i>a</i> (exp.)	<i>c/e</i> stroke to the left	<i>c</i> esprial	<i>ti/tj</i>	<i>l</i> -longa	<i>i</i>	ligatures with <i>i</i>																	
1115	ARG1183 Petrus Danieliz clericus iudex	N	<i>c</i>	Y	N (<i>ci</i>)	Y	Y	<i>e, g, l</i>	<i>b, d, m/n, t</i>	N	Y	N	<i>r</i>	N	N	N	Y	N	N	Y	<i>Y (t, b, h)</i>	Y	N	Y	
1130	AHUSBC* 198	N	N	Y	N (<i>ci</i>)	Y	Y	<i>e, g, l</i>	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N
1134	AHDS79.29 * Pelagius clericus	N	N	Y	N (<i>ci</i>)	Y	N	<i>g</i>	<i>b, c, l, m/n, r</i>	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y
1145	ARGVaam5 (1)5 Cresconius clericus.	N	N	N	N (<i>ci</i>)	Y	N	N	<i>b, i, m, t</i>	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	N	<i>Y (h, t)</i>	Y	N	Y	
1150	ARG497 Pelagius cardinalis	N	N	Y	N (<i>ci</i>)	Y	Y	<i>e, g, l</i>	<i>b, c, m/n, t</i>	N	Y	N	N	N	N	N	Y	N	Y	Y	<i>Y (h, t)</i>	Y	Y	Y	

TABLE 7. Scribes writing in cursive Visigothic script with Caroline minuscule influence in Santiago (see).

